

COOPERATIVE LEARNING AND ITS INFLUENCE TO PUPILS' IMPROVED LEARNING ATTITUDE AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE

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Cooperative Learning and its Influence to Pupils' Improved Learning Attitude and Academic Performance

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Abstract

The study attempted to determine influence of cooperative learning approach to pupils' learning attitude and academic performance among grade school pupils in the public school. Descriptive-correlational research method was utilized and the Statistical tools used in the study were mean, standard deviation, frequency count, and percentages to analyze the extent of the cooperative learning approach of teaching and pupils' learning attitude; the level of pupils' academic performance. Pearson-Product Moment Correlation was utilized to ascertain the significant relationship between the extent of cooperative learning approach and the level of pupils' learning attitude as well as in ascertaining the significant relationship between the level of pupils' learning attitude and their academic performance. Findings revealed that cooperative learning approach was to the "Very High Extent" utilized by teachers. Pupils develop their learning attitude to a "Very High Extent" and improve their academic performance. It was also found out in the statistical treatment of data that cooperative learning approach had a moderate correlation or relationship to pupils' learning attitude while learning attitude has negligible correlation to pupils' academic performance. As a summary, pupils' learning attitude was developed through the cooperative learning approach while pupils' learning attitude does not influence pupils' academic performance. Subsequently, it was recommended to the Schools Division Superintendent, School Principal, and Teachers to design and craft a cooperative and learner-centered strategic intervention material for the least mastered competencies to help improve pupils' learning engagement and academic performance.

Keywords: *cooperative learning approach, pupils' learning attitude, academic performance*

Introduction

Pupils learn systematically in an organize classroom activities into academic and social learning experiences as an approach of cooperative learning. Teachers structure pupils' interactions and prepare them for cooperation so that pupils work together in small groups supporting each other's learning processes.

The framework of the study is bounded on the context of legal and philosophical underpinnings pursuant to DO 31, s. 2012 on the immediate dissemination of and strict compliance of the order directed for independent and cooperative learning. The independent and cooperative learning are separate period ranging from two or four hours weekly may be provided as open time for learning.

Teachers who utilized cooperative learning arrange pupils into small heterogeneous groups structured to enhance the learning of all the group members. Additionally, Velasquez (2020) asserted that cooperative learning approach has gained popularity because it has influence pupils' improved learning attitude and academic performance since this approach aims to promote group cohesion by structuring group work based on social interdependence principle.

It was also emphasized that cooperative learning ensures that all group members are aware that they are dependent on each other's efforts in completing a task-a single member of a group cannot achieve anything unless all its members cooperate and must work in groups to complete tasks collectively toward academic goals.

Pinto, et al (2021) avowed that cooperative learning helps pupils learn cooperatively and collaborate with their peer's competence and skills such as asking the group members for information, sharing ideas and opinions, enhancing collaborative works. Additionally, teachers facilitate learning and ensure everyone succeeds when group succeeds.

In a similar investigation, Ross and Smyth (2021) described that successful cooperative learning approach as intellectually stimulating and creative, evidence-based, structured, and an effective tool for encouraging pupils to develop academic goals that stimulate them to participate with the tasks they are expected in order to achieve knowledge and skills.

However, Santiago, et al (2022) pointed out that cooperative learning is less effective learning approach and does not provide stronger support to the individual group member when the activities provided by teachers do not allow pupils full engagement and participation. Additionally, it was accentuated that some of the challenges of cooperative learning is group selection, the process by which teachers divide up pupils to participate in a cooperative learning activity; the roles of the group members; as well as the evaluation or assessment of the final group output.

It is based on the above-stated considerations that the researcher is stimulated to conduct this study to ascertain how cooperative learning influences to pupils' improved learning attitude and academic performance in Lumbia Central School in the City of Division of Cagayan de Oro for the school year 2022-2023.

Research Questions

The study aimed to ascertain the influence of cooperative learning to pupils' improved learning attitude and academic performance of Grade 3 pupils in Lumbia Central School of the City Division of Cagayan de Oro for the School year 2023-2024. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the cooperative learning approach of Grade 3 teachers in Lumbia Central School?
2. How does cooperative learning approach help improve pupils' learning attitude?
3. What is the level of pupils' academic performance when they are categorized as:
 - 3.1. outstanding;
 - 3.2. very satisfactory;
 - 3.3. satisfactory;
 - 3.4. fairly satisfactory;
 - 3.5. did not meet expectations?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the cooperative learning approach of teachers and pupils' learning attitude?
5. Is there a significant relationship between pupils learning attitude and their academic performance?

Methodology

Research Design

The study utilized the descriptive-correlational research design. Descriptive research according to Calderon, et al (2019) is a fact-finding inquiry or investigation. It is employed to develop a thorough knowledge of the primary causes of the given situations.

In addition, descriptive-correlational design as an inquiry used an in-depth analysis of the problem which data collection methods include, but not limited to the survey questionnaire and the like.

Subsequently, descriptive-correlational research design is used to quantify the problem by way of generating numerical data or data that can be transformed into usable statistics. This method measures variables through the use of quantifiable or finite data and the analysis was based on generated information from statistical tools. This method is also used in an inquiry with larger population.

Successively, descriptive data gathering procedures comprise different types of gathering information such as, but not limited to, the use of survey questionnaires, interview, and focused-group discussion (FGD).

Respondents

The respondents of the study were the Grade 3 teachers and pupils of Lumbia Central Schools of the City Division of Cagayan de Oro. There were forty-one (41) pupils whose learning attitude and academic performance have been observed and utilized in the study. The respondents were purposively chosen for the convenient accessibility of the researcher.

Instrument

The study was adapted from the research of Velasquez (2020) who asserted that cooperative learning approach has gained popularity because it has influence pupils' improved learning attitude and academic performance

The survey instrument is composed of two (2) major components. The first component will be on cooperative learning approach of teachers with ten (10) indicators. Additionally, the second component of the survey questionnaire will be on the pupils' learning attitude with ten (10) indicators while the third component is on pupils' academic performance which are categorized as outstanding, very satisfactory, satisfactory, fairly satisfactory, and did not meet expectations.

Procedure

The researcher asked permission from the Schools Division Superintendent through the recommendation of the Dean of the Graduate School and thesis adviser to conduct the study in the City Division of Cagayan de Oro.

The same permission was asked by the researcher to the parents of the pupil-respondents to allow their children to participate in the study and allow to use pupils' academic performance in terms of grades as variable of this study. Moreover, the parents were assured that the data gathered be treated to its highest confidentiality and will be used for research purposes only.

After the observation of pupil-respondents and interview, the researcher summarized and tabulated the data and submitted to the Statistician for analysis using appropriate statistical tools and techniques.

Data Analysis

The following statistical treatment are utilized to answer the different problems presented:

For Problem 1, mean and standard deviation were used to determine the extent of cooperative learning approach of teachers.

For Problem 2, mean and standard deviation were used to ascertain the pupils' learning attitude.

For Problem 3, Frequency and percentages were used to present the pupils' academic performance.

For Problem 4, Pearson r was utilized to ascertain the significant relationship between the cooperative learning approach and pupils learning attitude.

For Problem 5, Pearson r was utilized to ascertain the significant relationship between pupils' learning attitude and their academic performance.

For Problem 6, Pearson r was utilized to ascertain the significant relationship between cooperative learning approach and pupils' academic performance.

Results and Discussion

This section comprises the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of the finding resulting from this study on cooperative learning and its influence to pupils' improved learning attitude and academic performance as basis for interventions. The analysis and interpretation of data is carried out based on the problem presented.

Problem 1. What is the Extent of Cooperative Learning Approach of Grade 3 teachers in Lumbia Central School?

A cooperative learning approach involves pupils working together on activities or learning tasks in a group small enough to ensure that everyone participates. Pupils in a group may work on separate tasks contributing to a common overall outcome, or work together on a shared task.

Further, a cooperative learning classroom comprises pupils working in groups to achieve a learning task. The task is assigned by the teacher with specific instructions. Pupils will perform the learning tasks together with defined roles.

Table 1 shows the mean distribution of the extent of cooperative learning approach of teachers.

Table 1. Mean Distribution of Cooperative Learning Approach of Teachers

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
1. Motivates pupils to work with others in the class	4.94	.236	Very High Extent
2. Allows pupils to communicate with peers to master social processes such as participation and argumentation	4.95	.239	Very High Extent
3. Permits pupils to communicate with peers to master cognitive processes such as verification and criticism	4.94	.282	Very High Extent
4. Encourages pupils to collaborate peers to provide a forum for discovery learning	4.90	.349	Very High Extent
5. Inspires pupils develop creative thinking	4.86	.386	Very High Extent
6. Stimulates pupils to generate ideas.	4.64	.601	Very High Extent
7. Motivates pupils to form partnership to help peers	4.56	.696	Very High Extent
8. Supports pupils to improve academic performance	4.49	.756	Very High Extent
9. Helps pupil develop communication and interactive skills	4.31	.964	Very High Extent
10. Provides dynamic, appealing, and enjoyable learning environment	4.19	1.135	High Extent
Overall Mean	4.68	.564	Very High Extent

Legend: 4.21-5.00 Very High Extent/3.41-4.20 High Extent/2.61-3.40 Moderate Extent/1.81-2.60 Less/low Extent/1.00-1.80 No Extent

Table 1 displays the mean distribution of the extent of cooperative learning approach. Overall, the respondents rated the cooperative learning approach as "Very High Extent" with a mean of 4.68 (SD=.564). This result indicates that the cooperative learning approach was extremely utilized by teachers. It can be deduced based on findings that teachers involve pupils in working together on activities or learning tasks in a group to ensure that everyone participates and cooperates. Pupils in the group may work on separate tasks contributing to a common overall outcome, or work on a shared task.

Santiago, et al (2022) pointed out that cooperative learning is less effective learning approach and does not provide stronger support to the individual group member when the activities provided by teachers do not allow pupils full engagement and participation.

Additionally, it was emphasized that some of the challenges of cooperative learning is group selection, the process by which teachers divide up pupils to participate in a cooperative learning activity; the roles of the group members; as well as the evaluation or assessment of the final group output.

The indicator "Allows pupils to communicate with peers to master social processes such as participation and argumentation" obtained the highest mean value of 4.95 (SD=.239) which is verbally described as "Very High Extent" which implies that in cooperative learning approach teachers consent pupils to communicate with other learners in order to master their social skills through participation and cooperation with others in performing different learning tasks.

This finding was supported by Saldarriaga, et al (2021) who averred that cooperative learning consents learners to collaborate and participate with others in learning openly and improved learning attitudes and behavior and drive them to accelerate academic and

school performance. Further, it helps develop pupils' social skills and motivation to use them in group work sessions.

On the contrary, the lowest mean of 4.19 (SD= 1.135) which is verbally described as "High Extent" in the indicator "Provides dynamic, appealing, and enjoyable learning environment". The result indicates that cooperative learning approach provides dynamic and more gratifying as well as engaging learning experiences in the environment that is supportive to pupils' learning needs.

Gasser, et al (2021) pointed out that cooperative learning approach promotes social acceptance, social inclusion and strong cohesion among pupils who were enjoin to work cooperatively with other members of the class in a more enjoyable, dynamic, and pleasant learning environment. Additionally, this learning approach encourages the development of interactive skills and stimulates pupils to actively engage in the learning activities.

Problem 2. What does cooperative learning approach help improve pupils' learning attitude?

Pupils' learning attitude is generally developed through teachers' cooperative learning approach which is enthusiastic about their own learning. Pupils take ownership and responsibility when working as part of a team – possibly because other group members will be affected by their actions.

Cooperative learning is the recommended approach to modern day teaching especially in the outcomes-based education where teachers served as facilitators of the learning activities in the Philippe classroom.

Table 2. Mean Distribution of Pupils' Learning Attitude

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Description
1. Pupil learns with the intention of acquiring knowledge.	4.95	.227	Very High Extent
2. Pupil learns with the intention of improving cognitive and social skills.	4.95	.227	Very High Extent
3. Pupil learns to achieve academic goals and improve learning performance.	4.92	.257	Very High Extent
4. Pupil learns to avoid rejection from classmates, teachers, and parents.	4.89	.320	Very High Extent
5. Pupil learns to improve self-esteem and social support.	4.82	.398	Very High Extent
6. Pupil learns to help classmates improve performance.	4.60	.514	Very High Extent
7. Pupil learns in order to develop independence and life's skills.	4.51	.598	Very High Extent
8. Pupil learns to develop autonomy, responsibility, and achievements.	4.35	.734	Very High Extent
9. Pupil learns to enhance motivation and improve learning goals.	4.39	.765	Very High Extent
10. Pupil learns to achieve positive social status and approval from peers.	4.28	.978	Very High Extent
Overall Mean	4.67	.502	Very High Extent

Legend: 4.21-5.00 Very High Extent/3.41-4.20 High Extent/2.61-3.40 Moderate Extent/1.81-2.60 Less/low Extent/1.00-1.80 No Extent

Table 2 presents the mean distribution of the extent of cooperative learning helps pupils' learning attitude. Overall, cooperative learning helps to the "Very High Extent" pupils develop learning attitude with the mean of 4.67 (SD= .502) which indicates that pupils' attitudes towards learning are developed through the teachers' utilization of cooperative learning because it encourages the development of interpersonal skills and motivates pupils to participate more actively in the teaching and learning process.

The indicators "Pupil learns with the intention of acquiring knowledge" and "Pupil learns with the intention of improving cognitive and social skills" obtained the highest mean value of 4.95 (SD = .227) which indicate that through cooperative learning approach develop pupils' ability to learn to gain knowledge and with the intent of improving knowledge and social skills.

Pil, et., al (2022) disclosed that cooperative learning has positive relationships with cognitive and social skills development of the child. Pupils' cognitive and social skills are promoted when they are allowed to interact, share ideas and personal views, learn from each other, and the opportunity to agree and disagree with the group members.

On the contrary, the lowest mean of 4.28 (SD=.978) is verbally described as "Very High Extent" in the indicator "Pupil learns to achieve positive social status and approval from peers" indicates that the cooperative learning approach help pupils learn to achieve positive social approval from their peers or classmates. It can be deduced based on findings that it is imperative for teachers to utilize cooperative learning approach in teaching in order to help pupils achieve not only in their academic activities but also in their social and peer approval.

Herrera, et al (2022) averred that cooperative learning approach to pupils learning attitude and academic performance quantified that the learning approach is an effective tool to achieve positive social and approval from classmates and peer groups.

Problem 3. What is the level of pupils' academic performance when they are categorized as: Outstanding, Very Satisfactory, Satisfactory, Fairly Satisfactory, Did not meet expectations?

Table 3 presents the level of pupils' academic performance when they are categorized as Outstanding, Very Satisfactory, Satisfactory, Fairly Satisfactory, and Did not meet expectations.

It can be asserted that out of 169 respondents 110 (65%) were rated Satisfactory (80-85%) while only 15 or 9% were rated Fairly Satisfactory. It can be asserted that majority of pupils manifest reasonable academic performance through the utilization of teachers' cooperative learning approach. Subsequently, the cooperative learning approach is an educational strategy that help intensifies pupils' academic performance. Pupils will work in small groups, peers recognize that their rewards are dependent on the success of their

teammates and are more likely to provide support for each other's learning achievement.

Table 3. *Frequency Distribution of Pupils' Academic Performance*

<i>Performance</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Outstanding	0	0
Very Satisfactory	44	26%
Satisfactory	110	65%
Fairly Satisfactory	15	9%
Did not meet Expectation	0	0
Total	169	100%

Velasquez (2020) asserted that cooperative learning approach has motivated pupils to achieve the desired academic and learning performance as well as pupils' learning attitude. Further, it was emphasized that cooperative learning aims to promote group cohesion by structuring group work based on social interdependence principle which influence pupils' academic performance.

Problem 4. Is there a significant relationship between the cooperative learning approach of teachers and pupils' learning attitude?

Table 4. *Statistical Result of the Interplay Between the Cooperative Learning Approach and Pupils' Learning Attitude*

<i>Learning Approach</i>	<i>Pupils' Learning Attitude</i>			
	<i>(r)</i>	<i>Sig</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>H01</i>
Cooperative Learning Approach	.608	.000	Signifies moderate Correlation	Rejected

Table 4 presents the interplay between the cooperative learning approach and pupils' learning attitude. The table depicts that cooperative learning approach signifies moderate correlation to pupils' learning attitude as evident by the computed r value of .608 which is higher than the significant value of .000. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected. It can be argued logically, that pupils' learning attitude was significantly correlated with teachers' cooperative learning approach.

As Herrera, et al (2022) put it, cooperative learning approach influence pupils develop positive learning attitude which help improve academic performance and quantified that the cooperative learning approach is an effective tool to achieve positive social and approval from classmates and peer groups.

Problem 5. Is there a significant relationship between pupils learning attitude and their academic performance?

Table 5. *Statistical Result of the Interplay Between Pupils' Learning Attitude and Pupils' Academic Performance*

<i>Learning Attitude</i>	<i>Pupils' Academic Performance</i>			
	<i>(r)</i>	<i>Sig</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>H01</i>
Pupils' Learning Attitude	.109	.159	Indicates negligible Correlation	Accepted

Table 5 presents the interplay between the pupils' learning attitude and pupils' academic performance. The table depicts that pupils' learning attitude indicates negligible correlation to pupils' academic performance as evident by the computed r value of .109 which is lower than the significant value of .159. Thus, the null hypothesis was accepted. It can be argued logically, that pupils' academic performance was not correlated with pupils' learning attitude.

This finding was incongruent to that of Velasquez (2020) who avowed that pupils' learning attitude which was developed through cooperative learning approach influenced pupils' academic performance because cooperative learning approach has motivated pupils to achieve the desired academic and learning performance. Further, it was also emphasized that pupils' learning attitude through cooperative learning help promote pupils' social interdependence and cohesion which motivate them to perform better in their school and academic activities.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are drawn:

The Cooperative Learning Approach of teachers is an interactive and interdependent components of learning that boost the emotional and interpersonal experiences and awareness, judgment, critical analysis, flexible perspective taking, creative problem-solving, innovation, and goal-directed behavior because the approach provides opportunities to pupils to work together in heterogeneous, or mixed-ability, small groups. This teaching strategy is associated with increased pupil motivation, positive interaction, and improved academic performance.

Pupils' positive learning attitude develops through cooperative learning approach of teachers as it provides opportunities to every learner to associate, relate, and work collaboratively in small group tasks to accomplish the specified and desired output.

Cooperative learning approach of teachers benefits pupils' learning and academic performance because it develops positive learning attitude. It helps motivate pupils, improve learning outcomes, and develop skills such as critical thinking, communication, and cooperation.

Based on the findings and conclusions presented, the following recommendations are suggested:

Department of Education (DepEd) Officials will encourage teachers to utilize cooperative learning approach in order to help pupils develop positive attitude towards learning and develop collaboration in group work tasks with fellow learners to intensify social and academic skills. Additionally, intervention instructional materials that inspire cooperative learning activities should be developed by teachers through the technical assistance of the learning area education program supervisor.

School Principals/School Heads will inspire teachers to utilize strategies and teaching approaches that intensify learning and social skills of pupils or students such as a cooperative and learner-centered strategic intervention material for the least mastered competencies for learners in each learning area.

Teachers as Instructional Leaders are recommended to develop their cooperative and learner-centered strategic intervention materials responsive to the development of least mastered learning competencies in all learning area or subject area in order to improve not only the cognitive but the personal, social, and interactive skills of learners.

Parents will be able to provide support in the learning activities designed by teachers to improve their child's academic and learning performance. Parental support is indispensable in the academic success of their children, thus, the need to always encourage them to participate and collaborate with teachers in providing necessary learning support.

Community Officials/Other stakeholders will be able to provide more support to school activities especially in improving the pupils' social and interactive skills to address the problems on literacy and numeracy performance through the needed specific programs such as material support in development of more resilient cooperative and learner-centered strategic intervention materials to benefit the learners.

Future Researchers will be encouraged to conduct a similar study on the efficiency and effectiveness of the use of cooperative learning strategies and teaching approaches to improve pupils' learning attitude and academic performance as well as to identify the need of developing an intervention material to promote pupils' collaboration and engagements in the performance tasks to develop positive learning attitude.

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